

1 Photooxidation Effect in Liquid Lipid Matrices: Answers from an
2 Innovative FTIR Spectroscopy Strategy with “Mesh Cell”
3 Incubation

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23 **ABSTRACT**

24 Developing new approaches to evaluate the stability of edible oils under moderate
25 conditions is highly demanded today to avoid accelerated experiments that are not well
26 correlated with actual shelf-life. In particular, low intensity of visible light
27 (photooxidation) needs to be integrated in stability studies, together with mild
28 temperature. Thus, in this work, a strategy based on ‘mesh cell’-FTIR to monitor chemical
29 changes in lipid matrices using a combination of light and mild heating was applied. The
30 results were compared with those obtained for the stability of triolein used as a molecular
31 model. The study showed that the moderate light intensity (400 lx) at a low temperature
32 (23°C) has an early effect on the degradation of lipid matrices that is not observed when
33 they are stored at 35°C in the absence of light. Thus, the results proved that exposure to
34 light (400 lx) was more relevant than mild heating (35°C) in monounsaturated lipid
35 matrices, while polyunsaturated lipid matrices were more sensitive to mild heating.

36 *Keywords:* FTIR spectroscopy; mesh cell; photooxidation; edible oils; triolein;
37 combination of mild storage conditions.

38

39 **1. INTRODUCTION**

40 Currently, there is a marked demand from retailers and producers for analytical
41 tools to exert a major control on their products and to ensure that they comply with the
42 labeling regulation during their whole shelf life. At the same time, consumers are
43 demanding better quality of food products. Thus, they are paying more attention to the
44 “best before” date of fresh foods.

45 The prediction of the stability of fresh foods during their shelf life depends on the
46 complex interplay among several compositional variables, together with packaging and
47 environmental factors (moderate light and temperature). Fat food products, in particular,
48 are unstable because the chemical composition of their lipid fraction is sensitive to
49 oxidation. Thus, liquid lipid matrices, such as edible oils, are in continuous evolution of
50 their chemical composition because their fatty acid composition is susceptible to be easily
51 oxidized. The oxidative stability of oils depends on the ratio between polyunsaturated and
52 monounsaturated fatty acids composition. It has been estimated that the relative rate of
53 autoxidation of oleate:linoleate: linolenate is 1:40–50:100 in regards to oxygen uptake.^{1,2}
54 However, the effect of pigments, peroxides, phenols, and other minor constituents also
55 plays an important role in the oxidation process. Some of these compounds are removed
56 during the refining process. However, others remain in the oil having an influence in the
57 kinetics of the degradation. Thus, the degradation of the oil depends on the remaining
58 chemical compounds and the type of energy being exposed to the oil (heat, light, or both).

59 Considering how energy affects the rate of oxidation, it can be stated that the shelf
60 life of edible oils is greatly affected by variables that depend on the packer (type of
61 container, volume, etc.), the distributor and storekeeper (temperature, light, etc.). These
62 variables are not always suitable and perfectly controlled. Thus, they may affect the

63 kinetics of the oxidation process and modify the actual ‘best before date’ with respect to
64 the date declared on the label. The immediate consequence of failure in oil handling is
65 the decrease of the sensory quality of the product and the consequent consumer rejection,
66 thereby causing an image problem and economical losses. For that reason, maintaining
67 freshness along the food chain is of great concern to oil producers.^{3,4} Furthermore, gaining
68 knowledge about the alteration processes of different lipid matrices under real storage
69 conditions is also of interest for other food producers since edible oils are frequently used
70 in the elaboration of foods that undergo a quality loss over time influenced by their lipid
71 fraction.

72 Different studies have been focused on the stability of the oils under accelerated
73 conditions, mainly focusing on high temperatures that are close to 100°C.⁵ These studies
74 are based on the oil stability index (OSI) determined by Rancimat and the active oxygen
75 method (AOM).⁶⁻⁸ Although research with these methods has yielded relevant knowledge
76 that has helped in the understanding of oxidation mechanisms, the acquired information
77 is speculative, and it does not have a satisfactory correlation with the actual oxidation
78 process that slowly occurs at room temperature during the oil storage. Thus, the
79 degradation of oils is subjected to a different kinetic and degradation rate when they are
80 stored at a low temperature (<60°C).^{9,10} Another strategy is to store the samples under a
81 real condition, controlling temperature principally, during their whole shelf life.^{11,12} In
82 this strategy, the samples are periodically analyzed to check different quality parameters,
83 some of them, such as the peroxide value, are linked to the oxidative status of the oil and
84 inform us about the early stages in the oxidation process. However, it is important to note
85 that the aging of the oils at moderate conditions during distribution and storage is a
86 process that may take a long time (e.g., 12–24 months).¹³ Although this approach provides

87 realistic information, it cannot be easily implemented as a routine control, and, hence,
88 there are few studies carried out with real conditions of storage (e.g. moderated
89 temperature, 23-35 °C).

90 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) has been previously applied to
91 evaluate the quality of edible oils from different points of view. Thus, some parameters
92 of the edible oils related to the quality have been evaluated by FTIR, some of them being
93 free fatty acids,¹⁴ trans fatty acids,¹⁵ peroxide values,¹⁶ and iodine value.^{17,18} On the other
94 hand, the deterioration of virgin olive oil at a high temperature during frying also has been
95 monitored by FTIR.¹⁹ Recently, an accessory-named “mesh cell” was designed to monitor
96 the oxidation of edible oils by FTIR at room temperature; it was adapted and optimized
97 for assessing the stability of virgin olive oil.⁸ This accessory was used by García-
98 González and Van de Voort²⁰ for the first time to study the lipid oxidation process. In this
99 accessory, a thin monolayer of oil is incubated on a mesh and it undergoes a rapid
100 alteration. The chemical changes that take place in the oil are sequentially measured by
101 FTIR without the need of high temperature. Thus, the mesh cell is presented as an
102 excellent system of sample presentation to monitor the oxidation process (thermooxidation,
103 autoxidation, and photooxidation) under mild storage conditions of temperature and light
104 in a short period of time. In a previous work with this accessory,⁸ we reported that
105 moderate conditions, such as temperature at 35 °C or light intensity at 400 lx, have a
106 significant effect on the stability of different extra virgin olive oils that can be observed
107 in FTIR spectra. In this study, exposure to light at 400 lx, which is the intensity typically
108 found in supermarkets, proved to produce an increase in the content of hydroperoxides
109 and secondary oxidation products even at low temperature (23 °C). The photooxidation
110 process has been scarcely explored so far in the literature compared with thermooxidation.⁵

111 It is well-known that light has an important influence on oxidation, although this effect
112 decreases when the temperature increases.^{21,22} Few publications have been carried out
113 using high light intensities to evaluate their effects according to the composition of minor
114 compounds in virgin olive oil.²³ Even fewer studies about the effect of light on the
115 stability of refined lipid matrices exist. Furthermore, the study of the simultaneous effect
116 of more than one factor, such as a controlled combination of light and mild heating, in the
117 stability of different lipid matrices is a new alternative that can provide extra information
118 about the kinetics of the oxidation at real conditions of storage. This approach of
119 combining mild conditions of light and heating can be addressed with a mesh cell coupled
120 with the FTIR analysis.

121 One of the advantages of the incubation of oils in a mesh cell at mild conditions
122 for shelf life studies and the subsequent FTIR monitoring (mesh cell-FTIR) is the fact that
123 the design of the mesh cell accessory allows maximizing the changes in the spectral
124 regions associated with the primary and secondary oxidation products, such as
125 hydroperoxides and aldehydes. On the other hand, the spectra obtained with a mesh cell
126 also allow measuring changes in the spectral regions associated with the presence of
127 undesirable molecular structures, such as trans double bonds with an adequate signal-to-
128 noise ratio. Taking into account these advantages, the objective of this work is to evaluate
129 the effect of photooxidation at moderate light intensity (400 lx) in the stability of different
130 lipid matrices, virgin and refined, that can be found in multiple fat food products. A
131 sample of triolein (OOO) has been also included in the study as a molecular model to
132 compare the stability between samples with different fatty acid composition. Since OOO
133 does not contain minor compounds, this molecular model also allowed for the evaluation
134 of the effect of these compounds when results were compared with those obtained with

135 edible oils. The photooxidation is a process that occurs in combination with other
136 alteration processes as autoxidation. For that reason, three different combinations of
137 factors were taken into account in this study. These combinations were classified as
138 follows, “mild heating” (in the dark at 35 °C), “exposure to light” (400 lx at 23 °C), and
139 the “combination of mild heating and light” (400 lx at 35 °C), in order to study the
140 synergic effect of both oxidation factors.

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142 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

143 **2.1. Samples**

144 Four different lipid matrices were selected for this study. The first lipid matrix
145 was extra virgin olive oil (EVOO). The second lipid matrix used in the study was refined
146 olive oil (ROO) provided directly from the refinery. The third lipid matrix was a sample
147 of commercial linoleic sunflower oil (SO). The last one was a standard of triolein (OOO)
148 purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). The determination of fatty acid
149 composition of these samples was carried out by following the standard method
150 COI/T20/Doc No 33.²⁴

151 **2.2. Purification of triolein (OOO)**

152 In order to eliminate polar compounds that interfere in the initial oxidation state
153 of the sample, OOO was purified by using silica gel column chromatography with
154 hexane/ether (83:17 v/v) according to the standard IUPAC Method 2.507.²⁵ No
155 purification step was necessary in the other samples. After the purification, the
156 triacylglycerol analysis by GC²⁶ confirmed the declared purity for the OOO (~65%).

157 **2.3. Mesh cell-FTIR analysis**

158 The mesh cell, described in a previous work,⁸ was used to measure the degradation
159 of the samples under different mild conditions of light and temperature by FTIR
160 spectroscopy. Per each lipid matrix, a thin layer of sample (20 μ L) was deposited on the
161 mesh with a micropipette. The incubation of samples in the mesh cell was monitored
162 during 360 h by scanning one FTIR spectrum every 24 h. The spectra were acquired in
163 duplicate on a Bruker Vertex 70 FT-IR spectrometer (Bruker, Optics, Germany) equipped
164 with a deuterated triglycine sulfate (DTGS) detector. For the measurements, the mesh cell
165 was mounted in the transmission cell holder provided with the instrument. All spectra
166 were collected in the range of 5000–400 cm^{-1} by coaddition of the 32 scans at a
167 resolution of 4 cm^{-1} using weak Norton–Beer apodization. The spectra were collected
168 and manipulated with OPUS, version 7.2 (Bruker Optics, Ettlingen, Germany).

169 To facilitate the comparison between the replicates and samples, all of the spectra
170 obtained during the experiments were normalized to an effective path length of 110 μm .
171 The procedure to calculate the effective path length and normalize the spectra was
172 described in detail in a previous work.⁸ After the experiment, the cells were opened and
173 the meshes were cleaned with hexane in an ultrasonic bath at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h to be reused
174 in further experiments.

175 **2.4. Design of an in-house system to study the combined effect of mild light intensity** 176 **and mild heating by mesh cell-FTIR.**

177 Three different storage conditions were considered in this study: (i) mild heating
178 (in the absence of light at 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), (ii) exposure to light (visible light at 400 lx and at room
179 temperature, 23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), and (iii) combination of light and mild heating (exposed to visible
180 light at 400 lx and at 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The experiment under each condition was carried out in
181 triplicate for each sample. Thus, a total of 36 mesh cells were analyzed (four lipid

182 matrices, incubated at three storage conditions, analyzed in triplicate). An in-house
183 system was designed to produce these conditions and to evaluate the combined effect of
184 temperature and light. Figure 1 shows a scheme of this system. The compartment in the
185 system allowed for the 12 mesh cells to be simultaneously analyzed, and the dimensions
186 of this compartment guaranteed that all of mesh cells received the same light intensity
187 and temperature (Figure 1). The light source of the system was located above the mesh
188 cells compartment, which simulated the direction of the light when the product is exposed
189 in a supermarket. The light source used was a neutral white dimmable LED tube of 9 W,
190 and the intensity applied was regulated with a dimmer. The light intensity was controlled
191 with a digital lux meter, Trotec BF05 (Heinberg, Germany). The temperature was
192 controlled with a heater cable, 25 W and 5 m long, placed at the bottom of the
193 compartment that allowed a maximum temperature of 40 °C. The temperature and
194 humidity during the experiment were controlled with a digital thermometer and
195 hygrometer (TFA Dostmann, Wertheim, Germany).

196 **2.5. Statistical Analysis**

197 The peak heights relative to a selected single-point baseline were measured by
198 implementing macros programmed with the Macro/Basic tool provided in Omnic 9.8
199 (Thermo Scientific, Inc., Waltham, MA). Spectral data processing and statistical analysis
200 were conducted with Statistica 8 (StatSoft, Inc., Tulsa, OK).

201 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

202 The storage conditions used in this study were selected taking into account the
203 knowledge acquired in a previous study.⁸ In that work, it was shown that the most
204 moderate conditions (35 °C and light intensity at 400 lx) maximized the differences in the
205 oxidative stability of different extra virgin olive oils. These conditions allowed

206 differences in the shelf life of these oils to be established. Furthermore, it was
207 demonstrated that photooxidation, applying light intensities that are commonly found in
208 our daily environment (e.g., in a supermarket or a kitchen), has a relevant effect on the
209 oxidative degradation of virgin olive oils. In the present study, different combinations of
210 temperature and light were applied for studying the resistance to photooxidation of four
211 different lipid matrices and the relative importance of light with respect to mild heating.
212 These lipid matrices included virgin olive oil but also other edible oils that are subjected
213 to refining and are from different vegetable sources (refined olive oil and sunflower oil)
214 that are characterized with a different composition of major and minor components,^{27,28}
215 as well as OOO as a molecular triglyceride model. All the edible oils were fresh before
216 starting the experiments. In order to ensure the absence of polar compounds in the case
217 of OOO, this sample was subjected to a purification step consisting of passing the sample
218 through a silica gel column with hexane/ether (83:17 v/ v).²⁵ Figure S1 shows the effect
219 of this procedure on the OOO spectra. This shows the decrease in the intensity of the
220 spectral region assigned to hydroperoxides and alcohols (~ 3430 and 3534 cm^{-1} ,
221 respectively) after applying the purification step. The resulting spectrum was similar to
222 that of a fresh EVOO, also shown in the Figure S1.

223 The storage conditions selected for this study were close to the real storage
224 conditions that are attained during the distribution of edible oils, the transport, the storage
225 in the retailer, and the period of consumption at home. Thus, the samples were incubated
226 in three different conditions, “mild heating” (in the dark at $35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), “exposure to light”
227 (400 lx at $23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), and the “combination of mild heating and light” (400 lx at $35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). The
228 three storage conditions were achieved with an inhouse system designed to combine both
229 factors of light and temperature under mild conditions (Figure 1). It is important to note

230 that 400 lx is a light intensity typically found in supermarkets, while 35 °C is a
231 temperature that is low enough to be reached at any time during the transportation and
232 distribution of oils, and that is far enough from higher temperatures (60–100 °C)
233 implemented in accelerated oxidation procedures.⁶

234 Figure 2 shows the spectral changes of the four lipid matrices (OOO, ROO,
235 EVOO, and SO) incubated in mesh cells applying a combination of mild heating and light
236 during 360 h. As it can be observed in the raw spectra, five different bands present
237 changes during the experiment in all of the matrices. These bands, from high to low
238 wavenumbers, are assigned to (i) alcohols ($\sim 3535\text{ cm}^{-1}$); (ii) hydroperoxides (~ 3430
239 cm^{-1}); (iii) conjugated dienes ($\sim 1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$), associated with the C=C stretching
240 absorption of unsaturated carbonyl compounds; (iv) conjugated trans isomers (~ 987
241 cm^{-1}); and (v) isolated trans isomers ($\sim 967\text{ cm}^{-1}$).^{29–31}

242 With respect to the first band assigned to alcohols ($\sim 3535\text{ cm}^{-1}$), it provides
243 information about the evolution of the secondary oxidation products, as well as the band
244 assigned to unsaturated carbonyl compounds, probably aldehydes ($\sim 1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$).³⁰ Figure
245 2 shows that these bands (~ 3535 and 1640 cm^{-1}) present the maximum changes in the
246 SO matrix followed by the OOO matrix when they were stored at 400 lx and 35 °C. Thus,
247 these results pointed out that the most advanced oxidative degradation occurred in these
248 matrices compared with that of the other matrices, ROO and EVOO. Figure 2 also shows
249 that the bands of hydroperoxides ($\sim 3430\text{ cm}^{-1}$), isolated trans isomers ($\sim 967\text{ cm}^{-1}$),
250 and conjugated trans isomers ($\sim 987\text{ cm}^{-1}$) underwent an increment in all of the matrices.
251 The changes observed in these bands were more remarkable in the hydroperoxides band
252 than in the isolated trans isomers band in all cases (Figure 2). On the contrary, the slightest
253 changes were observed in the band assigned to conjugated trans isomers. These

254 differences can be verified in Table S1, which shows detailed information on these bands
255 in the four lipid matrices in the three conditions (mild heating, light, and both mild heating
256 and light). This information comprises the minimum and maximum peak height value of
257 each band, the increment of the peak height during 360 h of incubation, the standard
258 deviation of the changes underwent during the experiment, and the slope of the trend lines
259 obtained by representing the peak height versus the incubation time. This information
260 allows the evolution of each band between the storage conditions but also between the
261 lipid matrices to be compared. Thus, these results pointed out that the most consistent and
262 remarkable changes during the experiments are produced in the hydroperoxides band
263 ($\sim 3430\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Thus, the standard deviation for this band during the experiment ranged
264 between 0.01 and 0.42, while it was around ten times lower in the other bands, except for
265 the alcohol bands in SO, which reached 0.37 (Table S1). The changes observed in the
266 spectral region assigned to hydroperoxides consequently revealed the formation of
267 primary oxidation products.³² Thus, it can be concluded that all of the samples were in a
268 primary oxidation state at the end of the experiment, while for SO, and to a lesser extent
269 OOO, the alcohol bands proved that they were in a more advanced oxidation state.

270 In order to highlight the trend of the hydroperoxide band ($\sim 3430\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in all of
271 the experiments, the cumulative changes occurring in the spectra of the lipid matrices
272 over time under the three different storage conditions were determined by obtaining the
273 cumulative variance spectra computed on a daily basis.²⁰ These cumulative variance
274 spectra allow identifying changes at each moment and provide clear information on
275 small changes that may be confusing in raw spectra. Figure 3 shows the spectral region
276 of the hydroperoxides band in the cumulative variance spectra of the four lipid matrices,
277 OOO, ROO, EVOO, and SO, when they were incubated in mesh cells under the three

278 different storage conditions for the total period of the experiment (360 h). From the four
279 matrices, OOO can be regarded as a molecular model of a simple lipid matrix without
280 the minor compounds that are usually present in edible oils and acts as pro- or antioxidant.
281 Thus, the chemical changes determined in OOO can be only attributed to the
282 triacylglycerol composition (oleic acid) since no minor compound exerts any effect on
283 the oxidation of this matrix. The cumulative variance spectra of OOO reveals changes in
284 the band assigned to hydroperoxides in all of the storage conditions. As it is shown in
285 Table S1, the maximum peak height of the hydroperoxide band in OOO was higher when
286 a combination of mild heating and light was applied (0.52) compared with only exposure
287 to light (0.29) and only mild heating (0.14). This order in the formation of hydroperoxides
288 (combination of mild heating and light > exposure to light > mild heating) is similar in
289 the ROO and EVOO matrices. In these oils, light also was a factor that was more relevant
290 than only mild heating. However, this order was different in the SO matrix (combination
291 of mild heating and light > mild heating > exposure to light). Thus, this oil showed to be
292 highly sensitive to oxidation when it was heated at 35 °C. Thus, the maximum peak
293 height of the hydroperoxide band in this oil was 0.60 and 0.34 when applying mild
294 heating and exposure to light, respectively. The ratio between these two values resulted
295 in 1.8, which revealed the importance of mild heating in this lipid matrix.

296 The band assigned to alcohols ($\sim 3535\text{ cm}^{-1}$) was also shown in the cumulative
297 spectra displayed in Figure 3. This band was clearly observable in SO when applying a
298 combination of mild heating and light. The maximum peak heights of this band in all of
299 the samples followed the same order that was described above for hydroperoxide band
300 (Table S1). Thus, these results also prove that the influence of the exposure to light was
301 relatively higher than that of mild heating, except again for SO.

302 The fact that SO was more sensitive to mild heating than to light can be explained
303 by its fatty acid composition. Table 1 shows the composition in the percentage of fatty
304 acids of the samples studied in this work. SO is rich in polyunsaturated fatty acid
305 (58.66%), with the linoleic acid being the most abundant fatty acid (58.46%), while the
306 rest of oils were characterized by a major amount of monounsaturated fatty acids
307 (>81.92%).

308 In order to better compare the stability between matrices, the evolution of the
309 intensity of the band assigned to hydroperoxides ($\sim 3430\text{ cm}^{-1}$) was plotted against the
310 time of incubation (360 h). Figure 4 shows the trend lines of the hydroperoxides band
311 for the four matrices grouped according to the three storage conditions. Figure 4A shows
312 that all of the lipid matrices were quite stable when they were subjected to mild heating
313 (35 °C). Only SO and OOO underwent an increment of hydroperoxides under this
314 condition after 150 and 170 h, respectively. This increment can be explained by the
315 absence of the protective minor compounds, and in the case of SO, by its fatty acid
316 composition as described above.

317 Regarding the experience carried out with light (400 lx and 23 °C), Figure 4B
318 shows that all of the lipid matrices presented an increment of the hydroperoxide band
319 after the first 50 h, which evidenced the higher effect of photooxidation compared to the
320 mild temperature (35 °C). However, the speed of hydroperoxide formation is not the
321 same in all of the matrices. At the beginning of the incubation, the OOO sample presented
322 the fastest formation of hydroperoxide (Figure 4B), again being explained by the lack of
323 protection of the minor compounds. On the other hand, the SO underwent an acceleration
324 in the formation of the hydroperoxide after 250 h, being the most deteriorated sample at
325 the end of the experiment.

326 Finally, when samples are subjected to the combined action of light and mild
327 heating (Figure 4-C), the formation of hydroperoxides also was accelerated in greater
328 extent compared with the other storage conditions, overall in SO and OOO. Regarding
329 ROO and EVOO, they were the matrices that showed higher stability even when this more
330 drastic storage conditions was applied. In this case, ROO and EVOO matrices showed a
331 similar trend in the formation of hydroperoxides, but with slight differences in their
332 kinetics over time (Figure 4-C).

333 In general terms, Figure 4 shows that different conditions not only affect the final
334 values of the band assigned to hydroperoxides at the end of the experiment but also the
335 speed in their rising over time. Thus, the relative influence of light and temperature was
336 studied in terms of speed in the formation of hydroperoxides by means of the slopes of
337 trend lines (Table S1) and the ratios between different conditions. Figure 5 presents the
338 values of the slopes determined with the following equation:

$$339 \quad \text{Speed formation of hydroperoxide (slope)} = \frac{\Delta \text{band intensity at } 3430 \text{ cm}^{-1}}{\Delta t}$$

340 Thus, the effect of light (400 lx and 23 °C) in OOO, measured as the slope of the
341 trend line for the hydroperoxide band, is 4 times stronger than that of mild heating (35
342 °C). Thus, this high slope for OOO proves that monounsaturated triacylglycerols,
343 principally glyceryl trioleate, are more resistant to moderate temperature than to
344 photooxidation when no minor compounds are present. On the contrary, mild heating
345 was the most remarkable factor accelerating the formation of hydroperoxides in the SO
346 matrix. The slopes for this oil (Table S1) show a double effect of the mild heating in this
347 oil compared with that of light in regards to hydroperoxide formation. Finally, in the
348 case of ROO and EVOO, the slopes when exposing the samples to mild heating condition
349 were almost null, while exposure to light produced a slope slightly lower than that of

350 OOO. Therefore, it could be concluded that also in terms of oxidation speed, the effect
351 of light was more significant for monounsaturated lipid matrices (OOO, ROO, and
352 EVOO) than for polyunsaturated lipid matrices (SO), the latter being more sensitive to
353 mild heating.

354 This study pointed out that the effect of mild light intensity on the stability of
355 different lipid matrices may be more remarkable than that of the application of mild
356 temperature in some cases. In the case of mild temperatures, the degradation rate
357 measured as the intensity of hydroperoxide FTIR band seems to be strongly related to
358 the fatty acid composition and the presence of minor compounds. Thus, the SO matrix
359 of linoleic sunflower oil was presented as the most unstable sample when it was exposed
360 to 35 °C in dark. By contrast, SO oil exposed to light (400 lx at 23 °C) was 1.8 times
361 more stable than the same oil subjected to mild heating (kept in dark at 35 °C). In the
362 case of OOO, ROO, and EVOO, exposure to light showed a higher effect in the formation
363 of hydroperoxides compared with mild temperature.

364 All these results obtained with samples of different production sources (refined
365 vs virgin and sunflower seeds vs olives) highlight the importance of determining the
366 stability of the lipid matrices, including multiple factors (light in addition to mild
367 heating), and considering mild values of intensity. Thus, the combination of these two
368 factors, light (400 lx) and mild heating (35 °C), was presented as the best way to predict
369 the stability of the lipid matrices because this combination produced the highest
370 differences in the spectral bands when different oils were compared (Table S1). The in-
371 house system designed for combining different oxidation factors in a controlled way
372 (Figure 1) proved to be a useful tool to simulate the real conditions of the storage of fat
373 foods. With this combination of factors (both light and temperature) and the speed of

374 the oxidation process measured as the slope (Figure 5) being considered, the matrix that
375 was most stable under these conditions was EVOO, followed by ROO, OOO, and SO.
376 The last three oils were 1.14, 2.0, and 4.57 times more unstable than EVOO, respectively,
377 in terms of the FTIR band of hydroperoxides.

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384 **Supporting Information**

385 Details of spectra features (Table S1) as affected by each one of the three
386 conditions studied: mild heating, exposition to light and a combination of light and mild
387 heating; spectra of triolein (OOO) before and after purification and spectrum of extra
388 virgin olive oil (VOO) (Figure S1).

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489

490 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

491

492 **Figure 1.** In-house designed system to study the simultaneous effect of mild heating and
493 exposure to light in the oxidation process of lipid matrices.

494

495 **Figure 2.** Spectral changes of different lipid matrices when they are incubated in mesh
496 cells under conditions combining exposure to light and mild heating (400 lx and 35 °C
497 for 360h).

498 Note: Triolein (OOO), refined olive oil (ROO), extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) and
499 sunflower oil (SO). The scale of spectral regions that evolve during incubation has been
500 maximized and marked with an arrow, which indicates the direction of the evolution of
501 the band with time. The assignments of the spectral region are also indicated.

502

503 **Figure 3.** Spectral regions assigned to hydroxyl groups obtained for the cumulative
504 variance spectra computed from the spectra of triolein (OOO), refined olive oil (ROO),
505 extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) and sunflower oil (SO) in mesh cells for a total period of
506 360 hours (~15 days) under mild heating (kept in dark at 35 °C), exposition to light (400
507 lx and 23 °C) and combined action of light and mild heating (400 lx and 35 °C).

508 Note: The spectral bands that show changes during all the experiments are marked by an
509 arrow. The arrow indicates the tendency of the changes with the incubation time. The
510 chemical assignments of the spectral bands that present evolution are identified.

511

512 **Figure 4.** Time course trends of peak height for the spectral band at 3430 cm⁻¹ assigned
513 to hydroperoxides during 360 hours in the spectra of different lipid matrices when they

514 are stored in mesh cells subjected to three conditions: A, mild heating (kept in dark at 35
515 °C); B, exposure to light (400 lx and 23 °C); C, a combined action of light and mild heating
516 (400 lx and 35 °C).

517 Note: Triolein (OOO), refined olive oil (ROO), extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) and
518 sunflower oil (SO). The Y-axes have been set at the same value (0.35) to facilitate the
519 comparison of the trends. Some samples (OOO, SO) reached this value before 360 hours.

520
521 **Figure 5.** Speed of hydroperoxides formation determine by the trend lines slope of the
522 peak height of the spectral band at 3430 cm^{-1} during 360 hours in the spectra of different
523 lipid matrices loaded in mesh cells subjected to mild heating (kept in dark at 35 °C),
524 exposure to light (400 lx and 23 °C) and a combined action of light and mild heating (400
525 lx and 35 °C). Note: Triolein (OOO), refined olive oil (ROO), extra virgin olive oil
526 (EVOO) and sunflower oil (SO).

527

Table 1. Fatty acid composition (percentage) of selected samples.

Samples	OOO	ROO	EVOO	SO
Σ SFA	8.74	15.46	14.86	11.19
Σ MUFA	84.71	76.79	81.92	30.10
Σ PUFA	8.76	7.71	3.20	58.66
Σ UFA	93.47	84.50	85.12	88.76
C18:1	66.69	75.32	80.56	29.78
C18:2	6.49	7.06	2.59	58.46
C18:3	0.30	0.59	0.61	0.05

Note: OOO, Triolein; ROO, Refined olive oil; EVOO, Extra virgin olive oil; SO, Sunflower oil; Σ SFA, Sum of saturated fatty acids; Σ MUFA, Sum of monounsaturated fatty acids; Σ PUFA, Sum of polyunsaturated fatty acids.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

Table of Contents Graphics (TOC)

Supporting Information

Table S1: Minimum (min. peak height) and maximum (max. peak height) values of peak height of the bands assigned to alcohols ($\sim 3535\text{ cm}^{-1}$), hydroperoxides ($\sim 3430\text{ cm}^{-1}$), unsaturated carbonyl compounds ($\sim 1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$), conjugated *trans* isomers ($\sim 987\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and isolated *trans* isomers ($\sim 967\text{ cm}^{-1}$); increment of peak height (Δ height), standard deviation (SD) and slopes of the trend lines obtained by plotting peak height vs incubation time for the four lipid matrices when they are stored in mesh cell subjected to a combined action of light and mild heating (400 lx and 35 °C), exposition to light (400 lx and 23 °C) and mild heating (kept in dark at 35 °C) during 360h respectively.

Note:^a slope calculated in the range where the trend was linear; triolein (OOO), extra virgin olive oil (EVOO), refined olive oil (ROO) and sunflower oil (SO).

Lipid matrix/ storage condition	Min. peak height	Max. peak height	Δ height	SD	Slope (x10 ⁻³)
Alcohols (~3535 cm⁻¹)					
OOO/ 400 lx and 35 °C	0.05	0.25	0.20	0.07	0.60
OOO/ 400 lx and 23 °C	0.05	0.12	0.07	0.03	0.20
OOO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.05	0.08	0.03	0.01	0.01
ROO/400 lx and 35 °C	0.06	0.16	0.10	0.03	0.30
ROO/400 lx and 23 °C	0.07	0.11	0.04	0.01	0.10
ROO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.05	0.06	0.01	<0.01	<-0.02
EVOO/400 lx and 35°C	0.04	0.11	0.07	0.09	0.20
EVOO/400 lx and 23 °C	0.04	0.07	0.02	<0.01	0.07
EVOO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.03	0.04	0.01	<0.01	<0.01
SO/400 lx and 35°C	0.05	0.93	0.88	0.37	2.80
SO/400 lx and 23°C	0.05	0.14	0.10	0.03	0.20
SO/kept in dark at 35°C	0.04	0.36	0.32	0.10	0.70
Hydroperoxide band (~3430 cm⁻¹)					
OOO/ 400 lx and 35 °C	0.05	0.52	0.48	0.17	1.40
OOO/ 400 lx and 23 °C	0.03	0.29	0.26	0.09	0.80
OOO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.04	0.14	0.10	0.03	0.20
ROO/400 lx and 35 °C	0.03	0.31	0.28	0.09	0.80
ROO/400 lx and 23 °C	0.04	0.24	0.20	0.07	0.60
ROO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.03	0.04	0.01	<0.01	<-0.01
EVOO/400 lx and 35°C	0.03	0.29	0.26	0.09	0.70
EVOO/400 lx and 23 °C	0.03	0.20	0.17	0.06	0.50
EVOO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.03	0.04	0.01	<0.01	<0.01
SO/400 lx and 35°C	0.05	1.05	1.00	0.42	3.20
SO/400 lx and 23°C	0.03	0.34	0.31	0.11	0.80
SO/kept in dark at 35°C	0.04	0.60	0.56	0.20	1.60
C=C Stretching absorption of unsaturated carbonyl compound (~1640 cm⁻¹)					
OOO/ 400 lx and 35 °C	0.06	0.12	0.06	0.02	0.20
OOO/ 400 lx and 23 °C	0.08	0.12	0.40	0.01	0.10
OOO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.06	0.08	0.02	0.01	0.04
ROO/400 lx and 35 °C	0.06	0.11	0.05	0.01	0.09
ROO/400 lx and 23 °C	0.07	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	0.01
ROO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.06	0.07	0.01	<0.01	0.03
EVOO/400 lx and 35°C	0.08	0.10	0.02	0.01	0.07
EVOO/400 lx and 23 °C	0.06	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.04
EVOO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.06	0.07	0.01	<0.01	0.03
SO/400 lx and 35°C	0.12	0.43	0.31	0.15	1.10
SO/400 lx and 23°C	0.13	0.15	0.02	<0.01	0.02
SO/kept in dark at 35°C	0.12	0.16	0.04	0.01	0.05
Conjugated <i>trans</i> isomers (~987 cm⁻¹)					
OOO/ 400 lx and 35 °C	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.20 ^a
OOO/ 400 lx and 23 °C	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.10 ^a
OOO/kept in dark at 35 °C	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	-0.01 ^a
ROO/400 lx and 35 °C	<0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.07 ^a
ROO/400 lx and 23 °C	<0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01 ^a
ROO/kept in dark at 35 °C	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01 ^a
EVOO/400 lx and 35°C	<0.01	0.01	0.01	<0.01	<-0.01 ^a
EVOO/400 lx and 23 °C	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	-0.02 ^a
EVOO/kept in dark at 35 °C	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01 ^a
SO/400 lx and 35°C	<0.01	0.05	0.05	0.02	0.30 ^a
SO/400 lx and 23°C	<0.01	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.04 ^a
SO/kept in dark at 35°C	<0.01	0.60	0.60	0.20	0.20 ^a
Isolated <i>trans</i> isomers (~967 cm⁻¹)					
OOO/ 400 lx and 35 °C	0.28	0.33	0.05	0.01	-0.06
OOO/ 400 lx and 23 °C	0.14	0.18	0.04	0.01	-0.08
OOO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.08	0.30	0.22	0.07	0.10
ROO/400 lx and 35 °C	0.02	0.08	0.06	0.02	0.10
ROO/400 lx and 23 °C	0.04	0.05	0.01	<0.01	0.03
ROO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.04
EVOO/400 lx and 35°C	0.05	0.09	0.04	0.02	0.20
EVOO/400 lx and 23 °C	0.04	0.09	0.05	0.01	0.10
EVOO/kept in dark at 35 °C	0.03	0.04	0.01	<0.01	0.01
SO/400 lx and 35°C	0.01	0.05	0.04	0.02	-0.10
SO/400 lx and 23°C	0.05	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	-0.01
SO/kept in dark at 35°C	0.06	0.07	0.01	<0.01	-0.03

Figure S1. Different mesh cell-FTIR spectra of triolein (OOO) obtained before and after purification by passing the sample through a silica gel column according to the IUPAC method 2.507;¹⁹ for comparative purposes, the spectrum of extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) is overlaid.

